

Table 4: Documentation Items of OSF Registered Report Types

		RR.1	RR.2	RR.3	RR.4	RR.5	RR.6	RR.7	RR.8	RR.9	RR.10	RR.11
Metadata	Title	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Description	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Contributors	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Category	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Licensing	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Subjects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Metadata	Tags	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Study Information	Specific, Concise, and Testable Hypotheses	✓			✓							
Study Information	Research questions				✓							
Summary	Narrative Summary		✓									
Study Information	Research Aims			✓								
Study Information	Type of Aim			✓								
Study Information	Research question(s)			✓								
Study Information	Anticipated Duration			✓								
Design Plan	Study Type	✓										
Design Plan	Blinding Type	✓										
Design Plan	Factors and Treatments	✓										
Design Plan	Randomization	✓										
Design Plan	Study Design			✓								
Design Plan	Sampling and case selection strategy			✓								
Data Collection	Data source(s) and data type(s)			✓								
Data Collection	Data collection methods			✓								
Data Collection	Data collection tools, instruments or plans			✓								
Data Collection	Stopping criteria			✓								
Data Collection	Data collection status							✓				
Data Collection	Data access status							✓				
Data Collection	Other Comments							✓				
Data Description	Datasets used				✓							
Data Description	Data availability				✓							

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Data Description	Data access				✓							
Data Description	Data identifiers				✓							
Data Description	Access date				✓							
Data Description	Data collection procedures				✓							
Data Description	Codebook				✓							
Sampling Plan	Existing Data Use	✓										
Sampling Plan	Explanation of Existing Data	✓										
Sampling Plan	Data Collection Procedures	✓										
Sampling Plan	Sample Size and Rationale	✓										
Sampling Plan	Stopping Rule	✓										
Variables	Manipulated Variables	✓			✓							
Variables	Measurable Variables	✓			✓							
Variables	Combination of Variables in Index	✓										
Variables	Missing Data				✓							
Variables	Unit of Analysis				✓							
Variables	Statistical Outliers				✓							
Variables	Sampling Weights				✓							
Knowledge of Data	Prior Publication				✓							
Knowledge of Data	Prior knowledge				✓							
Analysis Plan	Statistical Models	✓			✓							
Analysis Plan	Data Transformation, Centering, and Recoding	✓										✓
Analysis Plan	Coding Scheme for Categorical Variables	✓										
Analysis Plan	Inference Criteria	✓			✓							
Analysis Plan	Data Exclusion	✓										✓

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Analysis Plan	Missing Data	✓										
Analysis Plan	Exploratory Analysis	✓			✓							
Analysis Plan	Approach			✓								
Analysis Plan	Process			✓								
Analysis Plan	Credibility strategies			✓								
Analysis Plan	Effect size				✓							
Analysis Plan	Statistical power				✓							
Analysis Plan	Assumption Violation				✓							
Analysis Plan	Reliability and Robustness Testing				✓							✓
Analysis plan	Rearriables											✓
Analysis plan	Statistical Technique											✓
Analysis plan	Variable Roles											✓
Analysis plan	Covariate Rationale											✓
Analysis plan	Other Techniques											✓
Analysis plan	Method of Correction											✓
Analysis plan	Assumptions of Analysis											✓
Analysis plan	Data Collection											✓
Analysis plan	Data Observation											✓
Analysis plan	Start and End Dates											✓
Analysis plan	Additional Comments											✓
Review Methods	Type of review					✓						
Review Methods	Review stages					✓						
Review Methods	Current review stage					✓						
Review Methods	Start date					✓						
Review Methods	End date					✓						
Review Methods	Background					✓						

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Review Methods	Primary research question(s)					✓						
Review Methods	Secondary research question(s)					✓						
Review Methods	Expectations / hypotheses					✓						
Review Methods	Dependent variable(s) / outcome(s) / main variables					✓						
Review Methods	Independent variable(s) / intervention(s) / treatment(s)					✓						
Review Methods	Additional variable(s) / covariate(s)					✓						
Review Methods	Software					✓						
Review Methods	Funding					✓						
Review Methods	Conflicts of interest					✓						
Review Methods	Overlapping authorships					✓						
Search Strategy	Databases					✓						
Search Strategy	Interfaces					✓						
Search Strategy	Grey literature					✓						
Search Strategy	Inclusion and exclusion criteria					✓						
Search Strategy	Query strings					✓						
Search Strategy	Search validation procedure					✓						
Search Strategy	Other search strategies					✓						
Search Strategy	Procedures to contact authors					✓						
Search Strategy	Results of contacting authors					✓						
Search Strategy	Search expiration and repetition					✓						
Search Strategy	Search strategy justification					✓						

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Search Strategy	Miscellaneous search strategy details					✓						
Screening	Screening stages					✓						
Screening	Screened fields / blinding					✓						
Screening	Used exclusion criteria					✓						
Screening	Screening instructions					✓						
Screening	Screening reliability					✓						
Screening	Screening reconciliation procedure					✓						
Screening	Sampling and sample size					✓						
Screening	Screening procedure justification					✓						
Screening	Data management and sharing					✓						
Screening	Miscellaneous screening details					✓						
Extraction	Entities to extract					✓						
Extraction	Extraction stages					✓						
Extraction	Extractor instructions					✓						
Extraction	Extractor masking					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Planned data transformations					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Missing data					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Data validation					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Quality assessment					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesis plan					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Criteria for conclusions / inference criteria					✓						

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Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesist blinding					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesis reliability					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesis reconciliation procedure					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Publication bias analyses					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Sensitivity analyses / robustness checks					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesis procedure justification					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Synthesis data management and sharing					✓						
Synthesis and Quality Assessment	Miscellaneous synthesis details					✓						
Publication Information	In-principle acceptance						✓					
Publication Information	Journal title						✓					
Publication Information	Date of in-principle acceptance						✓					
Manuscript	Attach manuscript						✓					
Other	Attach any supporting documents						✓					
Template from AsPredicted.org	Data collection								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Hypothesis								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Dependent variable								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Conditions								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Outliers and Exclusions								✓			

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		RR.1	RR.2	RR.3	RR.4	RR.5	RR.6	RR.7	RR.8	RR.9	RR.10	RR.11
Template from AsPredicted.org	Sample Size								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Name								✓			
Template from AsPredicted.org	Type of Project								✓			
Registering the Replication Attempt	Materials, procedures, analysis plan									✓		
Reporting the Replication	The effect size of the replication is									✓		
Reporting the Replication	The confidence interval of the replication effect size is									✓		
Reporting the Replication	The replication effect size is									✓		
Reporting the Replication	I judge the replication to be a(n)									✓		
Reporting the Replication	I judge it so because									✓		
Reporting the Replication	Interested experts can obtain my data and syntax here									✓		
Reporting the Replication	All of the analyses were reported in the report or are available here									✓		
Reporting the Replication	The limitations of my replication study are									✓		
The Nature of the Effect	Description										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Replication Importance										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Effect Size										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Confidence Interval										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Sample Size										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Original Study Conducted										✓	

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The Nature of the Effect	Region (original study conducted)										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Original Sample Size										✓	
The Nature of the Effect	Original Data Collection										✓	
Designing the Replication	Original Materials Available										✓	
Designing the Replication	Assumptions										✓	
Designing the Replication	Data Collection Location										✓	
Designing the Replication	Knowledge of Experimental Condition										✓	
Designing the Replication	Knowledge of Hypotheses										✓	
Designing the Replication	Sample Size Target										✓	
Designing the Replication	Sample Size Rationale										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Instruction Similarities										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Measure Similarities										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Stimuli Similarities										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Procedure Similarities										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Location Similarities										✓	
Differences between the Original and Replication	Remuneration Similarities										✓	

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